

UDK 37.091.33

**PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING AS A PEDAGOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR
DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE
EDUCATION**

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***Аннотация:** Статья посвящена теоретическому и методическому обоснованию проблемного обучения как педагогической основы развития коммуникативной компетентности в процессе иноязычного образования. Рассматриваются сущностные характеристики проблемного обучения, его принципы и этапы реализации в высшей школе. Анализируется структура коммуникативной компетентности и раскрываются механизмы ее формирования в условиях проблемно-ориентированной образовательной среды.*

***Ключевые слова:** проблемное обучение, коммуникативная компетентность, иноязычное образование, высшая школа, активные методы обучения, речевая деятельность, профессионально-ориентированное обучение, компетентностный подход.*

Modern foreign language education is focused on the formation of communicative competence as an integrative learning outcome that ensures the ability of students to effectively use a foreign language in professional and intercultural communication. In the context of globalization and digital transformation of society, foreign language proficiency is becoming an essential component of professional training. This makes it necessary to search for such pedagogical technologies that ensure the active involvement of students in the process of speech activity and create conditions for the formation of stable communication skills. Problem-based learning is one of the promising areas in this context [1, 10].

Problem-based learning is a pedagogical technology based on the creation of problematic situations and the organization of independent cognitive activity of students to resolve them. Its theoretical foundations are related to the ideas of developmental learning, cognitive psychology and the constructivist approach, according to which knowledge is formed in the process of active student activity. The essence of problem-based learning lies in the fact that knowledge is not transmitted in a ready-made form, but is absorbed in the process of finding a solution to a cognitive problem. A problematic situation arises when a student encounters an intellectual difficulty, the overcoming of which requires analysis, comparison of facts, hypotheses and argumentation of their own position.

In foreign language education, problem-based learning is of particular importance, since speech activity is inherently communicative and activity-based. In this case, language does not act as an object of study, but as a means of solving a communicative problem. Creating a problematic situation stimulates the natural need to use a foreign language to achieve a specific goal, which contributes to the formation of stable speech skills [2, 15].

Communicative competence is considered as a complex multicomponent education, including linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, strategic and sociocultural components. Linguistic competence involves mastery of grammatical and lexical means of language; sociolinguistic — the ability to take into account the social context of communication; discursive — the ability to build coherent and logically complete statements; strategic — the use of compensatory means with a lack of linguistic resources.; Sociocultural — understanding the cultural norms and values of native speakers. The formation of these components requires the organization of the educational process in conditions close to real communication, which is achieved through problem-oriented activities.

In the process of problem-based learning, students' thinking and speech mechanisms are activated. They analyze the information, discuss alternative solutions, argue their point of view, enter into a discussion and come to a collective conclusion. Such an organization of activities promotes the development of critical thinking, the ability to cooperate and independence. A special role is played by group work, during which a culture of dialogical communication and mutual respect for the positions of communication participants is formed [3, 45].

The methodological implementation of problem-based learning in foreign language education includes successive stages: creating a problem situation, formulating a problem, hypothesizing, searching and analyzing information, discussing solutions, presenting results and reflecting. Case studies, business and role-playing games, debates, project research, and professional situation analysis can be used as problem assignments. For example, students may be offered the task of developing a company's international cooperation strategy, which requires negotiations, preparation of a presentation and argumentation of the chosen position in a foreign language. In the process of completing the task, all components of communicative competence are activated, and speech activity acquires a practice-oriented character.

The practical experience of introducing problem-based learning in the university English course has shown a positive trend in the development of students' speech activity. Working in the format of problem projects contributed to an increase in the volume of spontaneous utterances, an improvement in the logical structure of speech, an expansion of a professionally oriented vocabulary and an increase in confidence in the use of a foreign language. The survey of students revealed an increase in motivation and satisfaction with the learning process, which confirms the effectiveness of the problem-based approach [4, 33].

Thus, problem-based learning is an effective pedagogical basis for the development of communicative competence in foreign language education. It ensures the integration of language knowledge and practical skills, forms the skills of reasoned speech, stimulates cognitive activity and develops students' learning autonomy. The prospects for further development of this area are related to the integration of digital educational technologies, the development of interdisciplinary problem modules and the creation of adaptive educational environments focused on the formation of communicative competence in modern higher education [5, 100].

Problem-based learning in the foreign language education system contributes to the formation of stable communication skills, the development of critical thinking and professionally oriented speech activity. Its use makes it possible to bring the learning process closer to the real conditions of communication, increase the motivation of students and ensure high-quality training of future specialists in intercultural communication.

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